

The Neutrosophic Axial Set theory

Mustafa Hasan Hadi^{1*} and L. A.A. Al-Swidi²

¹ Affiliation 1; Department of Mathematics, University of Babylon, Iraq; pure.mustafa.hassan@uobabylon.edu.iq

² Affiliation 2; Department of Mathematics, University of Babylon, Iraq; pure.leal.abd@uobabylon.edu.iq

* Correspondence: pure.mustafa.hassan@uobabylon.edu.iq

Abstract: We presented in this paper a new concept of sets that we launched it neutrosophic axial sets . These sets are considered as generalization of neutrosophic sets . The union relationships , intersection, union , belonging and other concepts were built on these sets , then we created two different concepts of points . Also we studied many important properties and basic theories about axial sets theory.

Keywords: neutrosophic sets; fuzzy sets; SNA -points ; NA -sets ; union relationships.

1. Introduction

The neutrosophic sets [1] are the important and influential topic in human life in direct way. It's considered to be one of the applied and pure topics at the same time .

Also it contributes to quantum leaps in the field of electronics , software and other sciences as well as in various engineering branches . Where Salama, A., FlorentinSmarandache, and Valeri Kromov who were the researchers first to know these sets in [2,3]. Researchers and scientists have taken it upon them and solves to develop and work on it . On the other hand , these sets are considered to be a development to the second type of fuzzy sets , which the researcher Zadeh , L. A. know in 1965 [4] introduced. At the same time , the fuzzy sets are generalized into so-called the soft sets which were defined in [5- 7] and attributed to Molodtsov [8]. There are many researchers who worked in this field and remind them of [9- 12].

In 2019 Abdulsada, D.A., Al-Swidi, L.A.A. defined a new concept of sets and called it the center sets , for more information , you can review the papers [13- 15] , and the pillar of construction is proximity spaces by . A. Naimpally and . D. Warrack [16], where we combined the proximity space with the i-topological space by Al Talkany, A.Y.K.M., AL-Swidi, L.A.A [17] to produce the i-topological proximity space in 2020 [18, 19]. These ideas can be generalized on the topic of neutrosophic.

2. The Neutrosophic Axial Set theory

2.1. Definition Let X be any set, the set of the form $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}A = \{ \langle A, A_1, A_2 \rangle ; A \cap A_i = \emptyset, i = 1, 2 \}$ is called neutrosophic axial set, where A be any subset of X , and the sets A_1, A_2 are called the parts of $\langle A, A_1, A_2 \rangle$. For example, if we take $X = \mathbb{R}$ the real numbers, then $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}A = \{ \langle (1, 2), A_1, A_2 \rangle ; (1, 2) \cap A_i = \emptyset, i = 1, 2 \}$ where

$$A_i = \begin{cases} \emptyset \text{ or discret set in } \mathbb{R} / (1, 2) \\ [2, x) & \text{for } x \geq 2 \\ (y, 1] & \text{for } y \leq 1 \end{cases}$$

2.2. Definition

I- Let X be any non-empty set, the neutrosophic point ($\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -point) are of the forms $\mathcal{N}P_A^\emptyset = \langle A, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle$, $\mathcal{N}P_A = \langle \emptyset, A, \emptyset \rangle$ and $\mathcal{N}P_A = \langle \emptyset, \emptyset, A \rangle$, for any proper non-empty subset A of X .

II- The singular neutrosophic point ($S\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -point) of any $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -set $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}A$ is denoted by $SA = \langle A, A_1, A_2 \rangle$, where $A \cap A_i = \emptyset$ where $i = 1, 2$, so $SA \in \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}A$ (where \in is the notion of classical belongs to).

So we can claim the number of $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -points of any non-empty universal set X is $|X|. (|P(X)/\{\emptyset, X\}|)$ where $|X|$ the number of elements of X .

Also from $|X|$ of above definition any $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -set is the classical union of its $S\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -points and any $S\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -point of any $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -set is neutrosophic set, but the converse is not true.

2.3. Definition

I- The empty $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -set with respect to the subset A of X is denoted by $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_{A}^\emptyset$ is of the form $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_{A}^\emptyset = \{ \langle \emptyset, A_1, A_2 \rangle ; \text{where } A \cap A_i = \emptyset \text{ } i = 1, 2 \}$. For example, if $X = \{ a, b, c \}$, then $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_{\{a,b\}}^\emptyset = \{ \langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle, \langle \emptyset, \{c\}, \{c\} \rangle, \langle \emptyset, \{c\}, \emptyset \rangle, \langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{c\} \rangle \}$.

II- The null $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -set with respect to a subset A of X , which denoted by $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}A$ is of form $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}A = \{ \langle A, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle \}$.

2.4. Definition

I- The $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -sum between two $S\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -points SA and SB is denoted by the notion \oplus_N which is defined by $S_A \oplus_N S_B = \langle A \cup B, C_1 \cup D_1, C_2 \cup D_2 \rangle$, where $C_i \cap A = \emptyset$ and $D_i \cap B = \emptyset, i = 1, 2$. So from this definition we claim that every $S\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -point is $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -sum of two or more than two $S\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -points, but every $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -point is $S\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -point.

II- The SNA -point SA is called interlaced with respect to NA -set NA_B , if $SA \in NA_B$ there exist $SB \in NA_B$ such that $A_i \subseteq B_i, S_A = \langle A, A_1, A_2 \rangle, S_B = \langle B, B_1, B_2 \rangle, i = 1, 2$. If any NA -point of the forms NP_A^\emptyset, NPA and NPA belong to NA -set NA_B , if A is a part of some SNA -point of NA_B . So that we easily show that, $SB \in NA_B$ iff $SB \in_N NA_B$.

III- The NA -set NA_A is said to be interlaced set with one of the NA -set NA_B which is denoted by $NA_A <_N NA_B$ iff for each $S_A = \langle A, A_1, A_2 \rangle \in NA_B$ there exist $SB = \langle B, B_1, B_2 \rangle \in NA_B$ with the condition $A_i \subseteq B_i, i = 1, 2$. Clearly every NA -set is interlaced set of NA_\emptyset , also NA_X is interlaced set of any NA -set.

2.5. Note

If $A \subset B$, then $NA_B <_N NA_A$. Because, for every SNA -point $SB = \langle B, B_1, B_2 \rangle \in NA_B$ that is $B \cap B_i = \emptyset$ and $A \subset B$ imply that $A \cap B_i = \emptyset$ for $i = 1, 2$, thus $SB \in NA_A$, which satisfy the condition of interlaced set. Two NA -sets NA_A and NA_B are called interwind sets which is denoted by $NA_A \approx_N NA_B$ iff $NA_A <_N NA_B$ and $NA_B <_N NA_A$.

2.6. Proposition

Let X be any sets and A, B are subsets of X . $A = B$ iff $NA_A \approx_N NA_B$.

Proof.

Assume that $A = B$, so by (Note 2.5), we get that $NA_A \approx_N NA_B$. Conversely, if possible that $A \neq B$.

Case 1. If $A \cap B = \emptyset$, then each $S_A = \langle A, A_1, A_2 \rangle \in NA_A$ and since each subset C of X with $C \cap B = \emptyset$ there is no SNA -points in NA_B which satisfy the condition of interlaced set, so NA_A is not interlaced set of NA_B . Similarly that NA_B is not interlaced set of NA_A , which contradiction with $NA_A \approx_N NA_B$.

Case 2. If $A \cap B \neq \emptyset$, that is there exist a point x in A and not in B or the point y in B but not in A , so $SB = \langle B, \{x\}, \{x\} \rangle \in NA_B$ imply that no SNA -points in NA_A which satisfy the condition of interlaced set, hence NA_B , similarly if we take $y \in B$ and y is not in A , which contradiction with $NA_A \approx_N NA_B$. Therefore we get $A = B$.

2.7. Definition

The NA - complement of any NA -set NA_A which is denoted by $(NA_A)^c$ and of the form $(NA_A)^c = NA_A^c$. Now we give the notions of union, intersection of NA -sets.

2. 8. Definition

The $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ – union of two $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -sets $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A$ and $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_B$, which is denoted by $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A \cup_N \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_B$ and is of the form $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A \cup_N \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_B = \{ \langle A \cup B, A_1 \cap B_1, A_2 \cap B_2 \rangle ; \forall \langle A, A_1, A_2 \rangle \in \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A, \langle B, B_1, B_2 \rangle \in \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_B \}$.Also for the same away we defined that for any collection $\{\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_{A_i}; i \in \mathbb{I}\}$ of $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ - sets , the $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -union of this collection is of form $(\cup_{i \in \mathbb{I}} \mathcal{A}_i)_N = \{ \langle \cup_{i \in \mathbb{I}} A_i, C_{j_1} \cap C_{j_2}, D_{j_1} \cap D_{j_2} \rangle ; \forall j_1, j_2 \in \mathbb{I} \}$ where $S_{A_{j_1}} = \langle A_{j_1}, C_{j_1}, D_{j_1} \rangle$ and $S_{B_{j_2}} = \langle B_{j_2}, C_{j_2}, D_{j_2} \rangle$.

The $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ – intersection of two $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -sets $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A$ and $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_B$, which is denoted by $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A \cap_N \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_B$ and is of the form $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A \cap_N \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_B = \{ \langle A \cap B, A_1 \cap B_1, A_2 \cap B_2 \rangle ; \forall \langle A, A_1, A_2 \rangle \in \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A, \langle B, B_1, B_2 \rangle \in \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_B \}$. Also for the same away we defined that for any collection $\{\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_{A_i}; i \in \mathbb{I}\}$ of $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ – sets , the $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -intersection of this collection is of form $(\cap_{i \in \mathbb{I}} \mathcal{A}_i)_N = \{ \langle \cap_{i \in \mathbb{I}} A_i, C_{i_1} \cap C_{i_2}, D_{i_1} \cap D_{i_2} \rangle ; \forall i_1, i_2 \in \mathbb{I} \}$ where $S_{A_{i_1}} = \langle A_{i_1}, C_{i_1}, D_{i_1} \rangle$ and $S_{B_{i_2}} = \langle B_{i_2}, C_{i_2}, D_{i_2} \rangle$.

The $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ –participating of two $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ -sets $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A$ and $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_B$, which is denoted by $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A \circledast \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_B = \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_{A \cap B}$.

It is easy to show that the commutative and associative properties for the $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ – union, $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ – intersection and $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}$ –participating are satisfied .

2.9. Proposition

For any set X and any subsets A, B , that is $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A \cup_N \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_B = \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_{A \cup B}$.

Proof .

For any $S_{\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}}$ -point $SD \in \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A \cup_N \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_B$, which of the form $SD = \langle A \cap B, A_1 \cap B_1, A_2 \cap B_2 \rangle$, with $S_A = \langle A, A_1, A_2 \rangle \in \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A, S_B = \langle B, B_1, B_2 \rangle \in \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_B$. Thus $SD \in \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_{A \cup B}$, because that $(A \cup B) \cap (A_i \cap B_i) = (A \cap (A_i \cap B_i)) \cup (B \cap (A_i \cap B_i)) = \emptyset$.

Conversely , now let $S_{A \cup B} \in \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_{A \cup B}$, if possible that $S_{A \cup B} \notin \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A \cup_N \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_B$, since $S_{A \cup B} = \langle A \cup B, D_1, D_2 \rangle$ with $(A \cup B) \cap D_i = \emptyset$, for $i = 1, 2$. But $\emptyset = (A \cup B) \cap D_i = (A \cap D_i) \cup (B \cap D_i)$, imply that $A \cap D_i = \emptyset, B \cap D_i = \emptyset$, so we have $\langle A, D_1, D_2 \rangle \in \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A$ and $\langle B, D_1, D_2 \rangle \in \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_B$, also $S_{A \cup B} = \langle A \cup B, D_1, D_2 \rangle = \langle A \cup B, D_1 \cap D_1, D_2 \cap D_2 \rangle \in \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A \cup_N \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_B$, which is a contradiction .

From this proposition we can prove easily the following corollary.

2.10 .Corollary

1. $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A \cup_N \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A^c = \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_X$.
2. $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A \cup_N \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A = \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A$.
3. $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_A \cup_N \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_X = \mathcal{N}\mathcal{A}_X$.

2.11. Remark

For any set X and subset A of X we have $\mathcal{N}A_A \cap_N \mathcal{N}A_X = \mathcal{N}A_A = \{ \mathcal{N}P_A^\emptyset \}$, because $\mathcal{N}A_A \cap_N \mathcal{N}A_X = \{ \langle A \cap X, \emptyset \cap A_1, \emptyset \cap A_2 \rangle ; \text{ for each } \langle A, A_1, A_2 \rangle \in \mathcal{N}A_A \} = \{ \langle A, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle \} = \{ \mathcal{N}P_A^\emptyset \} = \mathcal{N}A_A$.

2.12. Remark

Let X be any set with $\mathcal{N}A_A$ and $\mathcal{N}A_B$ are $\mathcal{N}A$ – sets on X . If $\mathcal{N}A_A <_N \mathcal{N}A_B$, then $(\mathcal{N}A_A \cap_N \mathcal{N}A_B) <_N \mathcal{N}A_A$ also $(\mathcal{N}A_A \cap_N \mathcal{N}A_B) <_N \mathcal{N}A_B$ because for any $\langle A \cap B, C_1 \cap D_1, C_2 \cap D_2 \rangle \in \mathcal{N}A_A$ from the fact $\langle A, C_1, C_2 \rangle \in \mathcal{N}A_A$ and $A \cap C_i \cap D_i = \emptyset$, for $i = 1, 2$. from above (Remark 2.12.) and (Note 2.5.) we have the following proposition.

2. 13. proposition

- 1- $(\mathcal{N}A_A \cap_N \mathcal{N}A_B) <_N \mathcal{N}A_{A \cap B}$.
- 2- $(\mathcal{N}A_A \cap_N \mathcal{N}A_B) \approx_N \mathcal{N}A_A$.
- 3- If $\mathcal{N}A_A <_N \mathcal{N}A_B$ and $\mathcal{N}A_B <_N \mathcal{N}A_C$, then $\mathcal{N}A_A <_N \mathcal{N}A_C$.
- 4- If $\sqsubseteq B$, then $\mathcal{N}A_A \cap_N \mathcal{N}A_B \approx_N \mathcal{N}A_B$.

Proof (4).

By (Note 2 . 5) and Remark (2 .12) we have $(\mathcal{N}A_A \cap_N \mathcal{N}A_B) <_N \mathcal{N}A_B$. Now let us $\langle B, D_1, D_2 \rangle \in \mathcal{N}A_B$, so $B \cap D_i = \emptyset$, but $A \sqsubseteq B$, then $A \cap D_i = \emptyset$ for $i = 1, 2$, then $\langle A, D_1, D_2 \rangle = \langle A \cap B, D_1, D_2 \rangle \in \mathcal{N}A_A \cap_N \mathcal{N}A_B$. So we get the result.

2. 14. Proposition

For any $\mathcal{N}A$ – points $\mathcal{N}P_D, \mathcal{N}P^D \in_N \mathcal{N}A_A$ which satisfy that, there exist a part C of some $S\mathcal{N}A$ – point of $\mathcal{N}A_B$ such that $D \sqsubseteq C$ iff $\mathcal{N}A_A <_N \mathcal{N}A_B$.

Proof.

Let $SA = \langle A, C_1, C_2 \rangle \in \mathcal{N}A_A$, then $\mathcal{N}A$ – points $\mathcal{N}P_{C_1}$ and $\mathcal{N}P^{C_2}$ are in $\mathcal{N}A_A$, so by assumption, there exist parts D_1, D_2 of $S\mathcal{N}A$ – points in $\mathcal{N}A_B$ with $C_i \sqsubseteq D_i$ and $B \cap D_i = \emptyset$, $i = 1, 2$, so $\langle B, D_1, D_2 \rangle \in \mathcal{N}A_B$, this imply that $\mathcal{N}A_A <_N \mathcal{N}A_B$.

Conversely, let $\mathcal{N}A_A <_N \mathcal{N}A_B$ and let $\mathcal{N}P_D \in_N \mathcal{N}A_A$, then the $S\mathcal{N}A$ – point $\langle A, D, \emptyset \rangle, \langle A, \emptyset, D \rangle$ or $\langle A, D, D \rangle$ are in $\mathcal{N}A_A$, then there exist $\langle B, C_1, \emptyset \rangle$. Such that $D \sqsubseteq C_1$ with $\mathcal{N}P_{C_1} \in \mathcal{N}A_B$ or $\langle B, \emptyset, C_2 \rangle$ such that $D \sqsubseteq C_2$ with $\mathcal{N}P^{C_2} \in \mathcal{N}A_B$ or $\langle B, H_1, H_2 \rangle \in \mathcal{N}A_B$ with $D \sqsubseteq H_i$, so $\mathcal{N}P_{D_1}$ and $\mathcal{N}P^{D_2} \in \mathcal{N}A_B$.

3. Conclusions

1. After an extensive study of these sets and spaces , we did this research establishing the basic structures for generalizing the neutrosophic sets , and under the name neutrosophicsets . Therefore , we can put the identification of the topological spaces on it , by taking a family of these \mathcal{N}_A – sets that achieve the following ; \mathcal{N}_X , \mathcal{N}_{\emptyset} belong it , second is closed under the finite \mathcal{N}_A – intersection , finally is must be closed under \mathcal{N}_A – union for any subfamily of it .
2. Also we can study their properties and characteristics , as well as define the functions on there to give as a good suggestions to work . Then , we can modify the various open sets and further study can be continued with this concept. For example , we can modify in the papers [20- 28] .

Acknowledgments:The authors remain thankful to the referee for his helpful suggestions and comments.

References

1. F. Smarandache. A Unifying Field in Logics: Neutrosophic Logic. Neutrosophy, Neutrosophic Set, Neutrosophic Probability, American Re-search Press, Rehoboth, NM, **1999**.
2. Salama, A., FlorentinSmarandache, and Valeri Kromov. "Neutrosophic Closed Set and Neutrosophic Continuous Functions." Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, **2014**, 4.1.
3. Salama, A. A., Alblowi, S. A., Smarandache, F. "Neutrosophic crisp open set and neutrosophic crisp continuity via neutrosophic crisp ideals". I.J. Information Engineering and Electronic Business, **2014**, vol. 3, pp.1 –8.
4. Zadeh , L. A. , Fuzzy sets , Inform. Control , **1965**, Vol. 8 , PP 338-353 .
5. Almohammed, R., AL-Swidi, L.A. , "New concepts of fuzzy local function " Baghdad Science Journal , **2020**, 17(2), pp. 515-522.
6. Al-Abbasi, H., Al-Swidi, L.A.A. , "On free-open sets " Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems", **2020**, 12(7), pp. 782-787.
7. Al-Swidi, L.A., Al-Rubaye, M.S. , " New classes of separation axiom via special case of local function , " International Journal of Mathematical Analysis, **2014**, 8(21-24), pp. 1119-1131.
8. Molodtsov , D. , Soft set theory first results , Comput. Math. Appl., **1999**, Vol. 37 , PP 19-31.
9. Al-Swidi, L.A., Al-Ethary, M.A. , "Compactness with "Gem-Set" , " International Journal of Mathematical Analysis,**2014**, 8(21-24), pp. 1105-1117.

10. Al-Swidi, L.A., Awad, F.S.S. , "Analysis on the Soft Bench Points ," ICOASE 2018 - International Conference on Advanced Science and Engineering, **2018** , pp. 330-335 ,.
11. Al Razzaq, A.S.A., Al Swidi, L.A.A.H. , "Soft generalized vague sets: An application in medical diagnosis", Indian Journal of Public Health Research and Development, **2019** ,10(2), pp. 901-907.
12. Hadi, M.H., AL-Yaseen, M.A.A.-K., Al-Swidi, L.A. , "Forms weakly continuity using weak ω -open sets " Journal of Interdisciplinary Mathematics **2020**.
13. Abdulsada, D.A., Al-Swidi, L.A.A. , "Separation axioms of center topological space " Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems , **2020**, 12(5), pp. 186-192.
14. Abdulsada, D.A., Al-Swidi, L.A.A. , " Some Properties of C-Topological Space " ,1st International Scientific Conference of Computer and Applied Sciences, CAS,**2019**, pp. 52-56.
15. Ali Abdulsada, D., Al-Swidi, L.A.A. " Compatibility of Center Ideals with Center Topology," IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering, **2020**, 928(4).
16. S. A. Naimpally and . D. Warrack , Proximity spaces , Cambridge Tracts No. 59, **1970** , Cambridge.
17. Mahdi Altalkany, Y.K., Al Swidi, L.A.A. , " Focal Function in i-Topological Spaces via Proximity Spaces " Journal of Physics: Conference Series, **2020** , 1591(1).
18. Al Talkany, A.Y.K.M., AL-Swidi, L.A.A. , " Ψ - operator proximity in i-Topological space ".Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education Research Article , **2021**, vol. 12, no. 1S, pp. 679-684.
19. Al Talkany, Y.K.M., AL-Swidi, L.A.A. , " New concepts of dense set in i-topological space and proximity space ". Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education Research Article, **2021**, vol. 12, no. 1S, pp. 685–690.
20. Abdulsada, D.A., Al-Swidi, L.A.A. , "Center Set Theory of Proximity Space" Journal of Physics: Conference Series, **2021**, 1804(1).
21. Al-Abbasi, H., Al-Swidi, L. , "Measurable SB-Functions Space and Confine MSB-Function Topology " Journal of Physics: Conference Series , **2021**, 1804(1).
22. Al-Abbasi, H., Al-Swidi, L.A.A., "Comparison between Confine MO-Connectedness and Connectedness, Confine MO-Countability and Countability" Journal of Physics: Conference Series , **2020**, 1591(1).

23. Al-Swidi, L.A., Mustafa, H.H. , "Characterizations of continuity and compactness with respect to weak forms of ω -Open sets ," European Journal of Scientific Research, , **2011**, 57(4), pp. 577-582.
24. Alswidi, L.A., Alhosaini, A.M.A. , " Weak forms of ω -open sets in bitopological spaces and connectedness ," European Journal of Scientific Research , **2011**, 52(2), pp. 204-212.
25. Abd Al-Haine Al-Swidi, L., Al-Fatlawe, I.J. , "On semi paracompactness and z-paracompactness in bitopological spaces ", European Journal of Scientific Research, **2010**, 47(4), pp. 554-561.
26. Al-Swidi, L.A.H. , "On preparacompactness in bitopological spaces ", European Journal of Scientific Research , **2010**, 46(2), pp. 165-171.
27. Hadi, M.H., Al-Yaseen, M.A.A.-K. , "Study of Hpre -open sets in topological spaces ," AIP Conference Proceedings 2292 , **2020**.
28. Al-Swidi, L.A., Awad, F.S.S. , " On soft turning points " Baghdad Science Journal, **2018** ,15(3), pp. 352-360.

Received: July 5, 2022. Accepted: September 19, 2022.